

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Tierberg Long Term Ecological Research site, Prince Albert, Western Cape, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: Surveys undertaken at Tierberg Karoo Research Centre, now known as Tierberg Long Term Ecological Research site near Prince Albert in the Western Cape, are reported on here. The plains landscape is characterised by circular biogenic patches 15–20 m in diameter, known as “*heuweltjies*”. These are over-dispersed at a density of 2.2/ha and overlie the subterranean nest of the termite *Microhodotermes viator*. The first annotated species list of spiders sampled from 1988 to 1990 is presented. A total of 103 species from 76 genera and 32 families were recorded. The most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (25 spp.), Salticidae (8 spp.), Lycosidae (7 spp.) and Zodariidae (6 spp.). The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species, as well as termite associations. Seven species are recognised as new.

Keywords: South African National Survey of Arachnida, Western Cape, conservation assessment, termites

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity is one of the most important concepts in contemporary biology, with a broad range of applications. In November 1995, South Africa ratified the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). Signatories are obligated to develop a strategic plan for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. To meet the requirements of the CBD, the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) was initiated in 1997. SANSA is an umbrella project implemented at a national level in collaboration with researchers and institutions countrywide, dedicated to document and unify information on arachnids in South Africa. SANSA’s aims are to: (1) discover, describe, and make an inventory of the arachnid fauna of South Africa; (2) organise all available information in a relational database and to make the data available to science and society; and (3) use this information to address issues concerning their conservation and sustainable use (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

One of the key accomplishments of SANSA was the First Atlas of South African Spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), which served as the basis for a national Red List assessment of South African spiders. This was largely made possible through the digitization of species-level specimen records in collections and records from taxonomic publications into the SANSA database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Due to extensive collecting done by SANSA fieldwork managers, specimen bycatches from other research projects, student projects, and through public participation in collecting specimens, more than 40 degree square grids were sampled in previously poorly sampled areas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). This effort has provided valuable material that has improved our knowledge of the distribution of species and provided specimens for future taxonomic studies. This database is now central in addressing questions around patterns of species richness and endemism and provided the basis for initial analyses of South African spider biodiversity with the finalising of the first ever national Red List assessment of spiders (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

Specimens in collections should not only be preserved, but the primary information associated with them contains valuable information on their distribution and general habitat. To make this

information available to science, surveys undertaken throughout the years, that contributed to the red listing project, have now been published as checklists. In the Western Cape, some of the published surveys include checklists of the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999), the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), and the Bontebok Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

This paper presents the first species list on the spider fauna of the Tierberg Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) site with information on their endemism and conservation status as well as association with termites.

METHODS

Study area: Most of the specimens were collected on the Tierberg Karoo Research Centre (TKRC), now known as the Tierberg LTER site. This 100-ha livestock enclosure was established on the sheep farm Tierberg in 1987 as part of Terrestrial Ecosystems Programme of the National Research Foundation that aimed to develop a predictive understanding of ecosystem structure and function in major biomes of South Africa (Arena *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 1. Plains at Tierberg LTER showing the termitaria “*heuweltjies*” as lighter patches. Photo credit: Suzanne Milton.

Figure 2. Open structure of dwarf shrubland on plains at Tierberg LTER. Photo credit: Suzanne Milton.

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Tierberg LTER lies at 33° 10' 06"S, 22° 15' 57"E and at an altitude of 745 m above sea level (a.s.l.), in the valley of the Sand River 20 km inland of the Swartberg mountains. The silty colluvial plains are flanked by Witteberg quartzite, Dwyka tillite, and Ecca mudstone hills (Fig. 1). The soils are silty and stony. Annual rainfall over the past 30 years averaged 195 mm and showed little seasonal pattern (summer = 56 mm; autumn = 62 mm; winter = 42 mm; spring = 36 mm) (Arena *et al.*, 2018). The dwarf shrubland vegetation of the area, Prince Albert Succulent Karoo (Mucina & Rutherford, 2006), is characterised by a mixture of succulent and non-succulent shrubs 0.1–0.4 m in height and dominated by *Pteronia pallens* and *Ruschia spinosa*. Grasses are restricted to drainage lines and the projected canopy cover at the time of the study ranged from 11–30% (Milton *et al.*, 1992). The plains landscape is characterised by circular biogenic patches 15–20 m in diameter known as “*heuweltjies*” (Figs 1 & 3). These are over-dispersed at a density of 2.2/ha and overlie the subterranean nest of *Microhodotermes viator* (Milton *et al.*, 1992). Vegetation cover on the alkaline and nitrogen-enriched soils of “*heuweltjies*” is dominated by succulents and salt-bushes and is generally denser than in the matrix vegetation of the plains (Milton *et al.*, 1992) (Fig. 2).

A few additional specimens were collected on the farm Botterkraal 15 km east of the Tierberg LTER at 33° 06' 09"S, 22° 23' 47"E, 916 m a.s.l. The soils at this site were coarser and sandier and the vegetation, classified as Gamka Karoo (Mucina & Rutherford, 2006), was denser (40% cover), dominated by non-succulent dwarf shrubs, particularly *Pentzia incana* and *Chrysocoma ciliata* (Milton, unpublished data).

Sampling methods and identification: On the Tierberg LTER, traps were set on “*heuweltjies*” and plains for 24 hours per month for 29 months between March 1988 and July 1990. Pitfall traps were tin cans embedded in the ground with the lip flush with the soil surface. The cans were 90 mm in diameter and when open, contained plastic bag liner containing water and glycol. When not in use, the lids were replaced to avoid excessive trapping effects on local populations of epigeic fauna.

On the plains, 20 pitfall traps were positioned in a grid of four rows 20 m apart, each with five traps at 5-m intervals. Twenty “*heuweltjies*” were selected on a “first encounter” basis and one trap was centred on each (Dean & Griffin, 1993). The total number of trap days on plains was 573 compared with 522 trap days on “*heuweltjies*” (Arena *et al.*, 2020). The catch was sorted and labelled the day after capture and specimens were sent to the National Collections of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria for identification and to deposit voucher specimens.

At Botterkraal, microarthropods on the soil surface were sampled by running a 12-V vacuum cleaner (intake width 33 mm) for 30 seconds across the soil in the open between shrubs and for a further 30 seconds below the canopy of shrubs (Dean & Milton, 2001). Faunal specimens collected in this way were labelled, preserved, and sent for identification as described above.

A survey of web spiders was conducted on 28 to 30 January 2017 at Tierberg LTER (Henschel & Lubin, 2018) to determine the impacts of livestock farming on arthropods and a range of related ecological processes. They sampled nine spider species from four web-building families. The study supports the hypothesis that web spider abundance is affected by shrub cover as they found that spider abundance is higher on densely vegetated mounds, termed “*heuweltjies*”, than in the surrounding shrub matrix in both the enclosure and the sheep pasture. The species of three of the families Agelenidae, Eresidae, and Theridiidae were also sampled from pitfall traps. Three species of the Araneidae of this study (*Argiope australis*, *Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus*, and *Isoxya cicatricosa*) were added to the checklist of spiders from Tierberg LTER.

Figure 3. The more succulent and closed vegetation on a “*heuweltjie*” at Tierberg LTER. Photo credit: Suzanne Milton.

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Endemicity value and conservation status of species: The global distribution of species was used to determine the endemicity value of each species (Table 3, Appendix 1). Values distinguished for species endemicity (E) are: (6) only known from the type locality (Tierberg LTER); (5) known from several localities in the Western Cape (WCE); (4) known also from Northern or Eastern Cape, the two adjoining provinces; (3) known from more than two provinces in South Africa (SAE); (2) known from other Southern African countries (STHE); (1) known from other countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE); and (0) also from countries outside the Afrotropical Region (CE). The conservation status of each species was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa where spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range the area of occupation was determined. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO, was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2-km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO. The distribution of threats across lineages were visualised using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within four categories: data deficient, least concern, rare, and threatened (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spider abundance by habitat: The traps captured a total of 754 individual spiders, of which 431 (or 82 per 100 trap days) were on “*heuweltjie*” habitat, and 323 (or 56 per 100 trap days) on the plains (Table 1). Thus, spiders, in common with ants (Arena *et al.*, 2017) were more abundant on the more productive “*heuweltjie*” habitat.

Table 1. The numbers of individual spiders in the genus *Ammoxenus* (Gnaphosidae) and other genera captured in pit traps on “*heuweltjie*” and plains habitats at Tierberg LTER.

HABITAT	NUMBER OF <i>Ammoxenus</i>	NUMBER OF SPIDERS	TOTAL	TRAP DAYS	NO./100 DAYS
Heu-weltjies	206	225	431	522	82.56
Plain	168	155	323	573	56.36
TOTAL	374	380	754	1 095	68.85

Species present: A total of 103 species in 76 genera and 32 families were recorded (Table 2; Appendix 1). Seven species were not identified to species level and are possibly new to science.

The Tierberg LTER material housed in the NCA since 1990 were available for taxonomic research and seven of the species were already included in several taxonomic revisions: *Seothyra schreineri* Purcell, 1903 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1990); *Peucetia viridis* (Blackwall, 1858) (Fig. 7) (Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994); *Tyrotama australis* (Simon, 1893) (Fig. 6) (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005); *Heriaeus allenjonesi* Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013; *Micaria beaufortia* (Tucker, 1923) (Fig. 8) (Booyens & Haddad, 2021), and *Mallinus nitidiventris* Simon, 1893 (Fig. 9) (Haddad *et al.*, 2019). Two species, *Langona warchalowskii* Wesolowska, 2007 (Fig. 10) and *Diploglena karooica* Haddad, 2015 (Fig. 12), were originally described with Tierberg LTER as the type locality. Of the four species of *Ammoxenus* collected at Tierberg LTER, one was identified as *Ammoxenus pentheri* Simon, 1896 (Figs 16–18) and the other three are new to science, but they still need to be described (Bird, 2003).

Family diversity: Of the 32 spider families collected from Tierberg LTER (Table 2; Appendix 1), the most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (25 spp.), Salticidae (8 spp.), Lycosidae (7 spp.), and

Zodariidae (6 spp.). Many of the species sampled at Tierberg LTER were also recorded during a survey in the nearby Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), where 186 spp. were sampled, with the Gnaphosidae (33 spp.) and Salticidae (23 spp.) the most species-rich families. The difference in number of species is due to sampling in Tierberg LTER restricted to the ground layer.

Table 2: Spider diversity of Tierberg LTER site with the total number of families, genera (G), and species (SP.) sampled.

FAMILY	G	SP.	FAMILY	G	SP.
Agelenidae	3	3	Palpimanidae	1	1
Amaurobiidae	1	2	Philodromidae	3	3
Araneidae	3	4	Phyxelididae	1	1
Caponiidae	2	2	Prodidomidae	3	3
Cheiracanthiidae	2	3	Salticidae	6	8
Clubionidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Corinnidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	1
Eresidae	4	4	Sicariidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	10	25	Sparassidae	3	4
Hersiliidae	1	1	Theridiidae	2	4
Linyphiidae	3	3	Thomisidae	2	2
Liocranidae	1	1	Trachelidae	1	1
Lycosidae	6	7	Uloboridae	1	1
Oonopidae	1	1	Zodariidae	6	6
Orsolobidae	1	1			
Oxyopidae	2	5		76	103

Conservation status: The majority (84.5%) of species have a wide distribution with no known threats and are therefore of least concern (LC) (Table 3). A small number (5.8%) are data deficient (DD), lacking taxonomic resolution or lack of distribution data. Only the new species were not evaluated (NE).

Endemicity: Eight species found at the Tierberg LTER have a cosmopolitan range and are also found outside the Afrotropical Region and were introduced to South Africa (Table 3). Twenty-two species are African endemics, while 31 species are Southern African endemics and 42 are South African endemics.

Three of the species, *Dresserus nigellus* Tucker, 1920 (Fig. 11) (Eresidae), *Purcelliana problematica* Cooke, 1964 (Fig. 4) (Prodidomidae), and *Diores bifurcatus* Tucker, 1920 (Fig. 5) (Zodariidae) have a restricted distribution and are Western Cape endemics. Presently no species are threatened and of special concern.

Termite associations: The research on the association of spiders with termites in South Africa has thus far only involved three widespread termite species, namely the harvester termite *Hodotermes mossambicus* (Hagen), dealt with by Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991), Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (1996 a, b); Petráková *et al.* (2015), *Trinervitermes trinervoides* (Sjöstedt) by Haddad and Dippenaar-Schoeman, and *Microhodotermes viator* (Dean, 1988).

Table 3. Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at Tierberg LTER site (DD– data deficient; NE – not evaluated; LC – least concern)

	NO. SPP.	CODE	%
CONSERVATION STATUS			
Data deficient	6	DD	5.8
Not evaluated	7	NE	6.8
Least concern	90	LC	87.4
Rare	0	R	0
ENDEMICITY			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	8	LC	7.8
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	22	LC	21.4
2 – Southern Africa endemics	31	LC	30.1
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE):	21	LC	20.4
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	10	LC	9.7
5 – Western Cape endemics (WCE)	3		3
6 – Tierberg LTER	7?		7

Ammoxenus was the most abundant genus and all the species are associated with termites. A total of 374 specimens were collected 49% of all spiders surveyed (Table 1). *Ammoxenus* species are agile, free-running, ground-living spiders. They have the ability to dive head-first into sand by using their modified chelicerae while holding their legs close to their bodies, hence the common name sand divers (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1996a).

The most extensive treatment of the biology of *Ammoxenus* species is given by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (1996a,b), with reference to *A. pentheri* Simon, 1896. (Figs 17 & 18). They are also known as termite-eating spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1996a) and all species of *Ammoxenus* seem to prey specifically on termites (Fig. 16). When the termites are inactive, these spiders bury themselves usually in the 20–60 mm high termite soil mounds of harvester termites near the termite foraging holes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1996b).

At Tierberg LTER, Dean (1988) observed an *Ammoxenus* species preying on the termite *Microhodotermes viator*. Worker termites emerge from foraging holes to cut fallen twigs into manageable pieces. The twigs are then dragged or carried to the nest entrances, from where other workers then drag the pieces into the nest system. The soldiers usually remain close to the foraging holes. Dean (1988) observed three attacks by an *Ammoxenus* on *M. viator*. He suggested that the spiders used tactile cues to select optimal prey items after initial handling of the prey. *M. viator* forages dynamically and unpredictably within a wide range of ambient and soil-surface temperature and humidity (Dean, 1993).

Other families associated with termites include the Gnaphosidae, Salticidae, and Zodariidae. Gnaphosids are mostly free-running, active ground dwellers and species of the genera *Asemesthes*, *Drassodes* (Fig. 13), and *Zelotes* were frequently sampled with termites and was observed feeding on them (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991).

In the Salticidae, species of *Heliophanus*, *Stenaelurillus*, and *Phlegra* have been associated with termites (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2006; Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991).

In the Zodariidae, species of *Diores* were observed feeding on termites (Jocqué, 1990, Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1992), while species of the smaller zodariids *Akyttara*, *Palfuria* (Fig. 15), and *Ranops* (Fig. 14) that were sampled at Tierberg LTER are associated with ants (Jocqué, 1990).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Charles Haddad and Neville Cornberg, as well as the late Peter Webb, Marie de Jager and Les Oates for the use of their photographs.

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Figures 4–18. 4. *Purcelliana problematica* (Prodidomidae). 5. *Diores bifurcatus* (Zodariidae). 6. *Tyrotama australis* (Hersiliidae). 7. *Peucetia viridis* (Oxyopidae). 8. *Micaria beaufortia* (Gnaphosidae). 9. *Mallinus nitidiventris* (Zodariidae). 10. *Langona warchalowskii* (Salticidae). 11. *Dresserus nigellus* (Eresidae). 12. *Diploglena karooica* (Caponiidae). 13. *Drassodes stationis* (Gnaphosidae). 14. *Ranops* sp. (Zodariidae). 15. *Palfuria* sp. (Zodariidae). 16. *Ammoxenus pentheri* (feeding on termite) (Ammoxenidae). 17–18. *Ammoxenus pentheri* (Ammoxenidae). Photo credits: 5–8, 10, 11, 13–15 Peter Webb; 9 Charles Haddad; 16 Marie de Jager; 12 Neville Cornberg; 17–18 Les Oates.

APPENDIX 1. Spiders of Tierberg LTER, Western Cape, listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CS), and global distribution (DST), possibly new species. [LC – Least Concern; DD – Data Deficient; NE – Not Evaluated; AE – African Endemic; STHE – Southern Africa Endemic; SAE – South Africa Endemic ; C – wider than Africa.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DST
Agelenidae	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Mistaria zuluana</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Olorunia punctata</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE
Amaurobiidae	<i>Pseudauximus pallidus</i> Purcell, 1903	4	LC	SAE
Araneidae	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
Caponiidae	<i>Caponia braunsi</i> Purcell, 1904	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Diploglena karooica</i> Haddad, 2015	2	LC	STHE
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona ansiae</i> Lotz, 2002	4	LC	SAE
Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
Corinnidae	<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
Dictynidae	<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
Eresidae	<i>Dresserus nigellus</i> Tucker, 1920	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Seothyra schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stegodyphus tentoriicola</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
Gnaphosidae	<i>Ammoxenus</i> sp. 1 *	6	NE	SAE
	<i>Ammoxenus</i> sp. 2 *	6	NE	SAE
	<i>Ammoxenus</i> sp. 3 *	5	NE	SAE
	<i>Ammoxenus pentheri</i> Simon, 1896	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes decoratus</i> Purcell, 1908	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Camillina procurva</i> (Purcell, 1908)	1	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina setosa</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes ereptor</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Megamyrmaekion schreineri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Poecilochroa anomala</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trephopoda parvipalpa</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus appendiculatus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DST
	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus communis</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus spiralifer</i> Purcell, 1907	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes fuligineus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes humilis</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
Hersiliidae	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
Linyphiidae	<i>Frontinellina locketi</i> Van Helsdingen, 1970	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
Liocranidae	<i>Rhaeboctesis secundus</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
Lycosidae	<i>Arctosa nivosa</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna bimaculata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pterartoria subcrucifera</i> (Purcell, 1903)	4	LC	SAE
Oonopidae	<i>Gamasomorpha humicola</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
Orsolobidae	<i>Azaniolobus</i> sp. *		NE	
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE
	<i>Peucetia maculifera</i> Pocock, 1900	2	LC	STHE
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus crudeni</i> Lessert, 1936	4	DD	SAE
Philodromidae	<i>Hirriusa variegata</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
Prodidomidae	<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Purcelliana problematica</i> Cooke, 1964	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Theuma capensis</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
Salticidae	<i>Heliophanus insperatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Kima variabilis</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> (Dufour, 1831)	0	LC	C
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DST
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes triangulifera</i> Purcell, 1904	4	DD	SAE
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops hessei</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
Sicariidae	<i>Loxosceles dejagerae</i> Lotz, 2017	3	LC	SAE
Sparassidae	<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE
	<i>Palystella pallida</i> Lawrence, 1938	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Palystes karoensis</i> Croeser, 1996	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Palystes castaneus</i> (Latreille, 1819)	2	LC	STHE
Theridiidae	<i>Latrodectus indistinctus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	0	LC	C
Thomisidae	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heriaeus allenjonesi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	3	LC	SAE
Trachelidae	<i>Afroseto porrecta</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	4	DD	SAE
Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
Zodariidae	<i>Akyttara</i> sp.*		NE	
	<i>Diores bifurcatus</i> Tucker, 1920	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Heradida extima</i> Jocqué, 1987	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Mallinus nitidiventris</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Palfuria</i> sp.*		NE	
	<i>Ranops</i> sp.*		NE	